

BECKMAN REACTION OF KETOXIMES OF THE TRICYCLO[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]DECAN SERIES WITH THIONYL CHLORIDE**Koshchii I.***PhD in Chemistry, Associate Professor**Department of Organic Chemistry and Technology of Organic Substances
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National Technical University of Ukraine "Igor Sikorsky Kyiv Polytechnic Institute"***ABSTRACT**

As a result of the Beckmann reaction, the oximes tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]decan-9-one, tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]dec-3-en-9-one and tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]dec-4-ene -9-one with thionyl chloride forms transmutation products - lactams and fragmentation products - unsaturated nitriles and isomeric chloronitriles.

Keywords: the oximes tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]decan-9-one, tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]dec-3-en-9-one and tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]dec-4-ene -9-one, lactams, unsaturated nitriles and isomeric chloronitriles.

Introduction

In works [1-3], we studied in detail the behavior of tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]decan-9-one, tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]dec-3-en-9-one and tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]dec-4-en-9-one in reaction with hydroxylamine-O-sulfonic acid. It was shown that the Beckmann reaction of all three framework substrates leads to the formation of both rearrangement products - lactams, and a significant amount of fragmentation products - unsaturated nitriles and oxynitriles, and conclusions were drawn about the carbenium ion mechanism of this process. However, it remained unclear whether such a mechanism is common for these objects in the Beckmann reaction or whether hydroxylamine-O-sulfonic acid plays a specific role here.

Results and discussion

To compare the studied version of the Beckmann reaction with the classical one, we decided to study the

reactivity of oximes (1), (5), (10) of the same framework ketones under the action of thionyl chloride. Ketoxime (10) and a mixture of ketoximes (1) and (5) in a 2:1 ratio (this is the ratio of the mixture of initial unsaturated ketones in [4]) were obtained using a known method [5]. Carrying out the Beckmann reaction of ketoximes (1), (5) with thionyl chloride in ether or benzene leads to the formation of compounds (2-4) and (6-9) (the composition of the reaction mixture was controlled by GLC, (table 1). Using liquid chromatography, it was possible to isolate compounds (2) and (4) in pure form, as well as three enriched fractions. The first of them consisted of 14.4% of compound (4) and 85.6% of compound (9), the second – of 38.7% of compound (6), 18.1% of compound (7) and 43.2% of compound (3), the third – of 69.1% of compound (2) and 30.9% of compound (8).

Table 1.

Properties of the reaction products of tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]decan-9-one (10) tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]dec-3-en-9-one (1) and tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]dec oximes -4-en-9-one (4) with thionyl chloride

# Subst.	yield, %		retention time, s	PMR spectrum ^{a,b} δ , ppm	IR spectrum, cm^{-1}
	ether	benzen			
1	2	3	4	5	6
2	39.7	74.5	657	c	1670, 3050 3090, 3200
3	6.6	10.6	414	4.25 c (1H, H ⁸), 5.28 (1H, H ³), 5.75 (1H, H ²)	
4	9.7	9.9	468	3.37m(1H, H ¹), 3.90m(1H, H ²), 5.65 c(2H, H ^{7,8})	2250, 3050
6	53.9	66.1	234	3.55m(1H, H ¹), 3.15m(1H, H ⁵), 5.57-5.59(2H, H ^{2,6}), 5.65(1H, H ⁷)	
7	16.7	6.8	270	5.74(1H, H ³) 3.84m(1H, H ⁵), 5.75(1H, H ⁴), 5.57-5.65(2H, H ^{6,7})	
8	7.6	3.9	594	c	1670, 3050 3090, 3200
1	2	3	4	5	6
9	8.7	5.7	504	4.40m(1H, H ²), 5.62(2H, H ^{6,7})	
11	42.3	21.6	240	3.29m(1H, H ¹), 5.55m(1H, H ²), 5.69m(1H, H ³)	
12	2.7	3.6	300	5.50(1H, H ³)	
13	8.9	6.5	270	5.50m(1H, H ⁴)	
14	26.0	55.4	675	c	1670, 3200
15 ^d	9.8	2.5	517	4.50m(1H, H ²)	
16 ^d	4.8	3.3	517	3.60m(1H, H ²)	

Note. ^a PMR spectra of mixtures of compounds were recorded. The percentage content, according to GLC data, is given in the experimental part.

^b Only the proton shifts used to identify compounds are shown.

^c The PMR spectrum is completely identical to that given in [1,2].

^d The content of compounds (6) and (7) in the mixture of products was determined using a glass column 2000x3 mm, 15% Apiezon L on an Inerton N-AW-HMDS carrier, program - 140-220°C (5 deg/min).

Compounds (2) and (8) turned out to be identical in PMR and IR spectra, respectively, to 10-aza-9-oxotricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]undec-3-ene and 10-aza-9-oxotricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]undec-4-ene, obtained in [2]. Compound (4), judging by the IR spectrum (Table 1) and elemental analysis, is an unsaturated chloronitrile. As can be seen from Table 1, in the NMR spectrum of this compound, signals from protons at the double bond and the proton adjacent to the chlorine atom are detected in a weak field. The third signal, having a fairly significant chemical shift (δ 3.37 ppm), may belong to the tertiary proton located in the β -position to the CHCl and CH=CH groups, which simultaneously have a deshielding effect on it. These data, as well as the similarity of the nature of the splitting of low-field signals with the corresponding signals in 4-cyanomethyl[3.3.0]oct-7-ene [2], allow compound (6) to be classified as 2-chloro-substituted derivatives 4-cyanomethylbicyclo[3.3.0]oct-7-ena.

The fraction consisting of compounds (4) and (9), as shown by IR spectra and elemental analysis, is a mixture of isomeric unsaturated chloronitriles. In the NMR spectrum of this mixture, the signal of unsaturated protons belonging to both chloronitriles, as in pure compound (4), has the form of a singlet. In addition, with the exception of the signals belonging to compound (4), only an unresolved multiplet at 4.40 ppm is observed in a weak field. (Table 1), which obviously belongs to the proton of the CHCl group in compound (9). The absence of a low-field signal of the tertiary proton (>3.0 ppm) indicates a greater distance of this group from the double bond than in chloronitrile (4). Thus, compound (9) is also a chloronitrile, a derivative of bicyclo[3.3.0]octane, isomeric to chloronitrile (4) both in the orientation of the chlorine and in the position of the double bond. Taking into account the above, as well as the analogy with oxynitrile derivatives having the same carbon skeleton [1, 2], the structure of 2-endo-chloro-4-cyanomethylbicyclo[3.3.0]oct-7-ene was assigned to

compound (4), and compound (9) – 2-exo-chloro-4-cyanomethylbicyclo[3.3.0]oct-6-ene.

In the IR spectrum of the mixture of compounds (3), (6) and (7), an absorption band of the nitrile group is observed (Table 1), which, judging by the relative intensity, is contained by all compounds included in this fraction. Compound (6) has the same retention time as 4-cyanomethylbicyclo[3.3.0]oct-2,6-diene, obtained and identified in [2]. Compound (7) has a retention time close to it (Table 1), which gives grounds to assume that it has the structure of a bisunsaturated nitrile. Compound (3) falls into the group of chloronitriles in terms of retention time (Table 1).

In the PMR spectrum of the mixture, a signal is observed at 4.25 ppm, which, in terms of integral intensity, refers to compound (3), and in terms of the chemical shift, obviously, to the proton of the CHCl group.

The fraction under study was hydrogenated on PtO₂ and, according to IR and PMR spectra, did not contain compounds with double bonds. Compounds (18) and (19) have the same percentage in the mixture as compounds (7) and (6), respectively, differing in retention time. Compound (19) had the same retention time as 4-cyanomethylbicyclo[3.3.0]octane [1]. The

Thus, based on spectral and synthetic data, compound (6) is 4-cyanomethylbicyclo[3.3.0]octa-2,6-diene, and compound (7), in all likelihood, is 3-cyanomethylbicyclo[3.3.0]octa-2,7-diene.

The interaction of ketoxime (10) with thionyl chloride in ether or benzene leads, according to GLC data (Table 1), to the formation of compounds (11-16). Chromatographically it was possible to isolate only

The nature of the signal (singlet) is similar to that of H8 in the spectrum of 6-cyanomethyl-8-hydroxybicyclo[3.2.1]oct-2-ene [2]. For this reason, as well as by analogy with the indicated oxynitrile, compound (3) can be assigned the structure of 8-chloro-6-cyanomethylbicyclo[3.2.1]oct-2-ene. Integration of the PMR spectrum of the mixture taking into account its composition determined by GLC method made it possible to determine that compound (7) contains only three unsaturated protons. In addition, signals are observed at 3.15, 3.55 and 3.84 ppm. If the first two certainly belong to the unsaturated nitrile (6) [2], then the third, judging by its intensity and relatively large chemical shift, can be attributed to the tertiary proton in compound (7), in the β-position to which there are two double bonds, deshielding his.

peak in the chromatogram corresponding to chloronitrile (3) disappears during hydrogenation, and the newly emerging peak of saturated chloronitrile, which does not coincide in retention time with any of the products of this composition (see below), probably corresponds to compound (18).

compound (14) in pure form, as well as a fraction consisting of compounds (11-13), (15), (16). Compound (14) turned out to be identical in PMR and IR spectra to 10-azatricyclo[5.3.1.0^{2,6}]undecan-9-one [1]. The IR spectrum of the mixture of the remaining reaction products contains an absorption band at 2250 cm⁻¹, characteristic of the nitrile group. Compounds (15) and (16) coincide in retention time with the hydrogenation products of chloronitriles (4) and (9).

In addition, the NMR spectrum of the mixture contains signals from the protons of the CHCl group at 3.60 and 4.50 ppm, which are also present in the spectrum of the hydrogenated mixture of chloronitriles (4) and (9) and apparently relate to H² in 2-exo-chloro-4-cyanomethylbicyclo[3.3.0]octane (15) and 2-endo-chloro-4-cyanomethylbicyclo[3.3.0]octane (16).

Analysis by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry showed that compounds (15) and (16) form molecular ions with the same *m/z* value of 183 (Table 2), but differ significantly in the stability of the [M-Cl]⁺ ion, which times more intense for the first compound. A decrease in the intensity of this ion in the mass spectrum of compound (16) is accompanied by an increase in the probability of the formation of fragment ions [M-CH₂CHCl]⁺, [M-C₅H₇]⁺ and [M-HCl-CH₂CHCN]⁺. This is consistent with the possibility of elimination of the chlorine radical with the assistance of the nitrile

group in compound (15) with the formation of a stable ion (20), which is difficult in the case of compound (16).

The correctness of the conclusions about the structure of compounds (15) and (16) was confirmed by an experiment in which oxynitrile (21) under the influence of thionyl chloride was converted into a mixture of unsaturated nitrile (11) and chloronitrile (16), while oxynitrile (22) in those Under the same conditions, it was converted almost exclusively into unsaturated nitrile (11) and chloronitrile (15).

A mixture of compounds (11-13), (15) and (16) was hydrogenated. In this case, only four compounds are formed. Two of them are identical in retention time to chloronitriles (15) and (16), and the rest are identical to nitriles (18) and (19), i.e. the double bond is found only in compounds (11-13).

Table 2

Mass spectra of products (4), (11-16) of the reaction of oximes (1) and (10) with thionyl chloride

# subst.	<i>m/z</i> (I, % of ion current)
4	183(0.30),182(0.33),181(0.91),146(1.46),145(1.46),143(1.65),141(3.10) 119(2.30), 118(2.14), 106(2.87), 105(2.24),104(2.13),91(2.87),79(2.80).
11	147(0.54),119(1.34), 118(3.08),107(20.35),106(3.88),105(3.88), 104(5.09), 91(6.69),80(2.14),79(26.77),78(3.35),77(4.42),67(1.61).
12	147(0.72),132(1.21),107(7.96),106(10.86),105(3.62),104(2.17), 91(5.31),80(7.96),79(24.13),78(2.42),77(4.58),67(8.93).
13	147(3.40),108(1.46),107(14.81),106(12.5),105(2.91),104(1.70), 91(8.13),80(2.43),79(24.27),78(3.76),77(4.49),67(1.46).
15	183(0.21),148(10.44),147(0.45),146(0.50),143(0.27),142(0.89), 131(1.10), 130(0.89),121(1.64),119(0.87),118(0.64),107(4.54),106 (5.63),105(1.85),104(1.27),91(1.80),81(2.78),80(3.88),79(7.95),67(8.34).
16	183(0.10),148(2.68),147(0.62),146(0.44),143(0.46),142(0.83),121(5.69) 119(0.90),118(1.39),116(3.24),107(6.11),106(3.15),105(1.23),104 (1.06),95(1.20),94(12.59),91(1.76),81(3.66),80(3.33),79(78.87),77 (2.55),67(10.18).

Analysis of the percentage composition of the mixture before and after hydrogenation suggests that

the unsaturated nitriles are 4-cyanomethylbicyclo[3.3.0]oct-2-ene (11), 4-cyanomethylbicy-

clo[3.3.0]oct-3-ene (12) and 3-cyanomethylbicyclo[3.3.0]oct-3-ene (13). Mass spectroscopy data confirm this (Table 2). Thus, a comparison of the mass spectra of compounds (11-13) shows that in terms of the relative intensity of the $[M-CH_2CN]^+$ and $[M-CH_3CN]^+$ fragments, compound (12) is much closer to compound (13), containing a cyanomethyl substituent of the double bond.

Conclusions

Thus, as a result of this study, it becomes clear that ketoximes (1), (5), (10), despite some differences in the reaction products, interact with thionyl chloride in the same way as ketones with hydroxylamine-O-sulfonic acid, i.e. e. the key stage of these processes is the synchronous cleavage of O-N and C-C bonds with the formation of a carbenium ion.

Materials and methods

IR spectra were obtained on a UR-10 spectrometer for 0.25% of the substance in a KBr tablet, a thin film with a layer thickness of 0.6 mm, or 1% solutions in CCl_4 . PMR spectra were taken on a Tesla BS-487C instrument, solvent CCl_4 , standard - HMDS. Mass spectra were obtained on a JEOL DX 300 gas chromatography-mass spectrometer. GLC analysis was carried out on a Tsvet-102 device, glass column 1000x3 mm, 5% XE-60 on Inerton N-AW-HMDS carrier, temperature 100-225 °C (10 degrees /min), carrier gas – helium (40 ml/min). The mixtures were separated by column chromatography on Silicagel 40/100 sorbent. To carry out reactions in ether, the method used in [6] was used.

Reaction of tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]deca-9-one oxime (10) with thionyl chloride. a. In benzene. To 1 g of oxime (10) in 30 ml of absolute tencol, 0.74 ml of $SOCl_2$ was added. Boiled for 1 hour. The reaction mass was washed with a 10% aqueous solution of Na_2CO_3 . After drying with Na_2SO_4 , the solvent was evaporated. We obtained 0.9 g (92.9%) of a mixture of compounds. GLC data, %: 21.3 (11), 3.5 (12), 6.4 (13), 61.6 (14), 3.1 (15), 4.1 (16).

b. On the air. From 1 g of oxime (10) we obtained 0.9 g (94.5%) of a mixture of reaction products, consisting, according to GLC data, of: 41.8 (11), 2.8 (12), 8.8 (13), 28.7 (14), 12.1 (15), 5.8 (16).

Reaction of tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]dec-3-en-9-one (1) and tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]deum-4-en-9-one (5) oximes with thionyl chloride. a. In benzene. 1 g of oxime mixture (1) (5) was added as described above. We obtained 0.9 g of a mixture of substances. GLC data, %: 55.4 (2), 8.8 (3), 8.2 (4), 21.6 (6), 2.2 (7), 1.4 (8), 2.4 (9).

b. On the air. From 1 g of a mixture of oximes (1) and (5) we obtained 0.65 g of a mixture of compounds. GLC data, %: 40.9 (2), 7.5 (3), 11.1 (4), 24.3 (6), 7.5 (7), 3.8 (8), 4.9 (9).

2-Endo-chloro-4-cyanomethylbicyclo[3.3.0]oct-7-ene (4). 4 g of a mixture of the reaction products of oximes (1) and (5) with $SOCl_2$, obtained by method a, was passed through a chromatographic column, sequentially eluting with a mixture of hexane and ether in a ratio of 10:1, 5:1, 5:2. Yield 0.4 g (48.9%) based on nitrile chloride loaded into the column (4). Found %: C 65.71; H 6.98; Cl 19.40; N 7.63.

$C_{10}H_{12}ClN$. Calculated %: C 65.78; H 7.10; Cl 19.44; N 7.67.

4-Cyanomethylbicyclo[3.3.0]octa-2,6-diene (6), 3-cyanomethylbicyclo[3.3.0]octa-2,7-diene(7), 8-chloro-6-cyanomethylbicyclo[3.2.1]oct-2-ene (3) was isolated similarly to compound (4). Yield 0.07 g. GLC data, %: 38.7 (6), 18.1 (7), 43.2 (3).

10-Aza-9-oxotricyclo[5.3.1.0^{2,6}]undec-3-ene (2) and 10-aza-9-oxo tricyclo[5.3.1.0^{2,6}]undec-4-ene (8). Lactams (2) and (8) were isolated similarly to compound (4). Eluent – methanol. Yield 1.1 g. GLC data, %: 69.1 (2), 30.9 (8).

2-Exo-chloro-4-cyanomethylbicyclo[3.3.0]oct-6-ene (9). The fraction enriched with chloronitrile (9) was isolated similarly to compound (4). Yield 0.07 g. GLC data, %: 14.4 (4), 85.6 (9). Found %: C 65.70; H 6.97; Cl 19.41; N 7.64. $C_{10}H_{12}ClN$. Calculated %: C 65.78; H 7.10; Cl 19.44; N 7.67.

Reaction of 4-cyanomethylbicyclo[3.3.0]octa-2-ol (21) with thionyl chloride. 0.1 g of oxynitrile (21) was dissolved in 2 ml of $SOCl_2$ upon cooling. The mixture was kept at 20-25°C for 24 hours. Thionyl chloride was distilled off together with CCl_4 . Yield 0.11 g. GLC data, %: 34.8 (11), 24.6 (15), 3.1 (16), 37.5 (21).

Reaction of 4-cyanomethylbicyclo[3.3.0]octa-endo-2-ol (22) with thionyl chloride. The reaction was carried out according to the procedure given for compound (21), starting from 0.1 g of oxynitrile (22). We obtained 0.1 g of a mixture of compounds. GLC data, %: 49.0 (11), 25.6 (16), 25.4 (22).

Hydrogenation of 8-chloro-6-cyanomethylbicyclo[3.2.1]oct-2-ene (3). 0.06 g of a mixture consisting of 38.7% compound (6), 18.1% compound (7), 43.2% compound (3) was dissolved in 3 ml of methanol, 0.02 g of PtO_2 was added. The suspension was stirred for 0.5 hours, purging with hydrogen. After filtering, the solvent was evaporated. Yield 0.06 g. GLC data, %: 35.3 (19), 18.4 (18), 46.3 (17). IR spectrum (cm^{-1} , CCl_4): 2250, no absorption band at 3050. PMR spectrum (δ , ppm, CCl_4 , HMDS): no signals in the region of 5.0-6.0.

Hydrogenation of 2-endo-chloro-4-cyanomethylbicyclo[3.3.0]oct-7-ene (4) and 2-exo-chloro-4-cyanomethylbicyclo[3.3.0]oct-6-ene (9). 0.07 g of a mixture consisting of 14.4% compound (4) and 85.6% compound (9) was dissolved in 2 ml of methanol, and 0.01 g of PtO_2 was added. Then proceeded as described in the previous method. Yield 0.07 g. GLC data, %: 13.9 (16), 86.1 (15). PMR spectrum (δ , ppm): 3.60 (1H, CHCl), 4.50 (1H, CHCl).

Hydrogenation of a mixture of the reaction products of tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]decan-9-one oxime (10) with thionyl chloride. 0.9 g of the mixture of products obtained by method a was passed through a chromatographic column, eluting with a mixture of hexane and ether in a ratio of 1:1. We obtained 0.35 g of a mixture of compounds. GLC data, %: 55.3 (11), 9.2 (12), 16.7 (13), 8.1 (15), 10.7 (16). Then eluted with methanol. We obtained 0.53 g of compound (14) (96.4% of what was loaded into the column). The first fraction was dissolved in 10 ml of methanol, and 0.03 g of PtO_2 was added. the suspension was stirred, purging with hydrogen at room temperature for 10 minutes.

After filtering, the solvent was evaporated. We obtained 0.35 g of a mixture of compounds. GLC data, %: 65.5 (9), 16.7 (18), 8.1 (15), 10.7 (16).

References

1. Isaev S.D., Klimko Yu.E., Vulfson N.S., Liepins E.E., Sekatsis I.P., Yurchenko A.G., Chernyaev B.V. // ZhOrKh. 1989. T.25. Vol. 5.S. 954-964.

2. Isaev S.D., Klimko Yu.E., Vulfson N.S., Liepins E.E., Sekatsis I.P. Yurchenko A.G., Sinelnikov S.I., // ZhORKh. 1989. T.25. Vol. 5. P. 965-976.

3. Klimko Yu.E., Isaev S.D., Yurchenko A.G., Chernyaev B.V. // Zh.Orkh. 1989. T. 25. Issue. 5. pp. 977-984.

4. Bruson H.A., Riener T.W. // J. Am. Chem. Soc. 1945. Vol. 67. P. 727-736.

5. Klimko Yu.E., Isaev S.D., Yurchenko F.G., Chizhov O.S. // Bulletin of the KPI. Ser. chem. mechanical engineering and technology. 1984. No. 21. pp. 3-6.

6. Kovacic P.K., Field K.W., Wnuk T.A. // J. Chem. Eng. Data. 1971. Vol. 16. # 2. P. 141-142.